

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONVERGENCE PROCESS OF TWO TYPES OF STANDARDS: IFRS AND US GAAP

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Abstract. This article discusses the relevance of the transition of enterprises to international financial reporting standards in modern conditions. The regulatory framework required for the transition to the international financial reporting system (IFRS) is provided. Attention is also paid to the most significant differences in Russian accounting standards (RAS) and international standards. The authors also consider accounting models for enterprises in accordance with IFRS and the stages of bringing financial statements to international standards. In addition, the article considers groups of enterprises that are required to maintain financial accounting in accordance with international standards.

Keywords: IFRS, RAS, financial reporting, international standards, accounting standards, accounting transformation.

Introduction.

Starting from the 1960s and 1970s, scientists began to think about the transformation of the world into a single global system, and already in the 1990s, the process of globalization became very relevant. Most countries strive to create a healthy and sustainable economy, which is due to a combination of various factors: these are the conditions for the development of small and medium-sized businesses, which contribute to the formation of the middle class – a fundamental element of civil society; and the investment climate - conditions conducive to the inflow and outflow of foreign capital into the country; and the "tax conditions" that determine the creation of a business; and the creation of conditions for the development of transnational corporations (TNCs), which are a kind of engine of globalization; and many other factors. There are two main factors that embody the problem of accounting and reporting in TNCs: the first is that a huge amount of money, human

and time resources are required to maintain accounting and provide financial statements in accordance with the principles of the two countries; The second factor is the difficulty of comparing and comparing the principles of two different countries. However , as part of the process of economic integration and unification in 1973 , Through the joint efforts of professional accounting organizations in 10 countries (Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Mexico, Japan, the Netherlands, England, Ireland and the USA), the International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC) was established, which proclaimed its main goal to unify and harmonize accounting principles everywhere

[<http://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf/history/resource25>].

The consistent development of this committee and the expansion of the base of standards required for the preparation and presentation of financial statements are indicators of the ongoing globalization and the desire of the IASC to overcome the problems of TNCs, which were listed above. The main purpose of this work is to analyze the gradual formation and development of the process of convergence of two types of standards: American generally accepted accounting standards and IFRS, starting from the formation of the IASC (1973) and ending in 2012. (the study of the convergence process of the two standards ends in 2012 due to the lack of reliable and objective information for the subsequent period). First of all, we will consider the formation and the beginning of the work of the IASC with the release of the first standards (the period from 1973 to early 2002). Next, we will analyze the actions of the IASC and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) in relation to the convergence process and its speed. Looking ahead, it should be noted that the rate of convergence was much higher during the George W. Bush administration (2002-2009), while during the Barack Obama administration (from January 2009 to the end of 2012, since our analysis ends this year), there were significantly fewer

incentives for the development and completion of convergence, and consequently, the convergence rate was small. Thus, having considered the gradual development of the process of convergence of IFRS and US GAAP, we will analyze, firstly, the possible problems of the international financial reporting standards themselves, which are designed to be the unifying force of the standards of most countries: secondly, the quality of American and international standards; and thirdly, the readiness of the world itself for a high speed of globalization. IASC's inception (1973-2002) As mentioned above, the IASC was formed in 1973. The main goal is to develop and publish accounting standards related to the provision of public financial statements, and to improve and harmonize them. In this part of the paper, we will talk about how the IASC began its work, what changes its structure underwent and what standards were the first. The structure of the IASC Since the formation of the IASC, it has been the main body that has developed international standards for the provision of financial statements. However, it was not a committee in the literal sense, rather it was a structure consisting of several components that had certain tasks and functions.

Initially, the structure of the IASC looked like this. The IASC Management Board, or IASC Board, was responsible for the direct development of accounting standards, their interpretation and the drafting of a conceptual structure. This body included only 13 participating countries, but it was also possible to include an additional one or three organizations that acted as freelance employees. Each member or participant of the IASC Board represented two delegates and one technical adviser, i.e. the number of people participating in the debate and making decisions (voting) could vary from 39 to 48. In addition, the governing body could include persons who only had the status of observers, i.e. they could participate in debates, but were not allowed to vote; as a rule, these were representatives of the

European Commission, FASB and the International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO) [<http://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf/history/resource25>]. It should be noted that often some companies and bodies that establish national accounting standards directly used the principles that were developed by the IASC, but did not pass further approval. After the IASC developed the standards, the advisory group, the second component of the committee structure (Advisory Group), which included a variety of international organizations interested in accounting, gave advice on the developed standards. At the next stage of adoption of the developed standards, the Standing Interpretations Committee (or SIC) operated. The main function of this committee was to collect and present public opinion on the developed standards, assuming that these principles were finally approved. The next component of the IASC structure was the Advisory Council, which was an oversight body. And finally, as the last instance of standards (not so much the development and adoption, as the settlement and resolution of various difficulties), there were Steering Committees, which were expert task forces on various projects. 24 years later (in 1997), the IASC concluded that the convergence of national accounting standards and high-quality international standards is necessary, which is impossible without restructuring the committee itself and changing its strategy. As a result, restructuring work began at the end of 1997. First, the so-called Strategic Working Party was created, which was supposed to revise the structure and strategy of the committee. In December 1998, the Strategy Working Party summarized its activities in a report that provides recommendations for changing the structure and strategy. After some improvements, the final version was submitted in November 1999, which was immediately adopted by the IASC. The remaining IASC structures approved the plan in May 2000. Thus, the new "constitution" of the IASC came into force on July 1, 2000. The new structure is

shown in Figure 1. This model, in some important respects, is based on the structure of the US Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB). The management – the Board of Trustees - seeks funds, receiving them from a wide range of sources (including corporations, audit firms and market regulators) and appoints members of the Management Board (International Accounting Standard Board - IASB), the Standards Advisory Council (SAC) and the Interpretation Committee (International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee - IFRIC). He also controls the compliance of the Board's activities with its constituent documents. The Board of the IASB is fully responsible for all substantive issues, including the preparation and publication of IFRS, their drafts, and also makes a final decision on the approval of clarifications (interpretations) to the standards. Now the advisory board, the Interpretation Committee and the Standards Development Board are under the guidance of the IFRS Foundation, which in turn is managed by 22 trustees. The functions of this body are very broad and diverse, therefore, we will list only a few of them: developing, in the public interest, a set of high-quality, understandable and universally accepted financial reporting standards that are equipped with mechanisms for execution (these standards should be transparent, clear, comparable and useful for users of financial statements); promoting the widespread use and application of these standards; facilitating easier adaptation of standards; appointment of IASB, SAC and IFRIC members, etc. [<http://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf/governance/ifrsf>]. The IASB, renamed the IASB, should develop and publish high-quality international standards that will ensure transparency and comparability of financial statements of companies. The Advisory Board should advise the IASB on priority areas, inform it about the application of standards and public opinion on the developed standards. And, accordingly, the committee on interpretations is engaged in the development of

interpretations of international standards and regulation of other issues [<http://www.iasplus.com/en/resources/ifrsf/governance/ifrsf>].

This system is intended to allow the management board to develop a set of high-quality financial reporting standards acceptable for use in international securities markets and capable of serving as a model for the convergence of various systems of national standards. To do this, the board will need to convince national authorities with relevant functions to approve the use of international standards: the board does not have its own direct authority for this. An important point for this was IOSCO's approval of the list of IFRS, but IOSCO simply recommends that its members adopt international standards; which does not oblige them to do so at all. The American Securities and Exchange Commission is a leading participant in IOSCO, and its requirement that the use of international standards in American markets be accompanied by recalculation in accordance with American national standards is a major obstacle to the dissemination of IFRS. For this reason, the program currently being implemented to introduce a number of changes to IFRS and American national standards to ensure their convergence is very important. In addition, the Board of the IFRS Council and the US Financial Reporting Standards Committee have committed themselves to finding the best solutions to certain issues. The approaches developed in this way will be implemented both in IFRS and in US national standards. However, the board may face obstacles not only in the USA. During the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards, all countries or their regulatory authorities will probably try to retain some kind of veto or choice, which allows them to avoid applying those aspects of IFRS that they consider unacceptable. If such a law is widely applied, it may call into question the very possibility of achieving true international comparability. The European Commission's decision on IAS 32 and IAS 39 (standards on Financial instruments)

may become a precedent case in this regard. Currently, the Commission has approved all other standards inherited by the IASB from the predecessor organization, but these two faced strong resistance in Europe, especially from banks, and the approval of IFRS (IAS) 32 and IFRS (IAS) 39 was postponed until final amendments were made to them [Malofeeva, 2006]. Before proceeding to the description of the first standards issued by the IASC, a small feature should be noted: before the restructuring of the committee (i.e., until 2000-2001), international standards were issued under the name IAS (International Accounting Standards); After the change in the structure of the committee, the standards issued not by the IASC, but by the IASB, were called IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards) [PwC Academy, 2015, pp. 15-18]. Since in this part of the work we are considering the work of the IASC in the period from 1973 to 2002, we will briefly study the first standards issued by the committee during this period (i.e. IFRS issued by the IASB and IAS issued later in 2001-2002 will not be considered; a brief study of the standards is due to the fact that this is not the main purpose of this work). The first standard (IAS) 1 "Presentation of Financial Statements" entered into force on January 1, 1975, however, a new version of this standard, taking into account the changes developed in 2007, re-entered into force on January 1, 2009. The main purpose of this provision is the comparability of the company's financial statements for previous periods and the financial statements of other organizations. (IAS) 1 includes information on recommendations on the structure and minimum requirements for the content and presentation of financial statements [PwC Academy, 2015, pp. 34-58]. Later, in 1978, IAS 8 "Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors" was published (the new version (IAS) 8, including the latest changes, came into effect on January 1, 2005). This standard is used when a company selects, adopts and changes its accounting policy, changes accounting

estimates and corrects errors identified in previous periods. (IAS) 10 "Events after the Reporting Date" has been in effect since January 1, 1980 and takes into account changes in 2005. This standard describes the rules for accounting and reporting in the financial statements of events that occurred in the period after the end of the reporting period and before the approval of the financial statements prepared by the company. On January 1, 1981, IAS 12 "Income Taxes" came into force (amendments of 1998 were taken into account), which establishes the procedure for accounting for income taxes, namely current and future tax consequences. (IAS) 16 "Fixed Assets" was put into effect from January 1983, taking into account the changes from 2005. This standard describes the principles of accounting for fixed assets. In 1984 two standards have come into force: (IAS) 17 "Leases", which describes the principles of accounting and "disclosure of information regarding financial and operating leases for tenants and landlords", and (IAS) 20 "Accounting for government subsidies and Disclosure of information on state aid", which defines the accounting procedure for government subsidies and their reflection in the financial statements. Similarly, two standards were issued in 1985: (IAS) 19 "Employee Benefits", which describes the accounting procedure for employee benefits and the disclosure of this information; and (IAS) 21 "Effect of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates", disclosing information on the procedure for including transactions performed in foreign currency and foreign activities in the financial statements, as well as on the translation of financial statements into the presentation currency. (IAS) 23 "Borrowing Costs" and (IAS) 24 "Disclosure of Information about Related Parties" were issued in 1986. The first standard takes into account the changes of 2009 and sets the permissible level of capitalization of borrowing costs incurred due to raising funds to finance the purchase of assets [PwC Academy, 2015, p. 189]. The second standard takes into account the changes of 2011 and defines the

conditions and procedure for reflecting information about transactions with related parties (i.e. with subsidiaries and associates) in the financial statements (this precaution is necessary due to the fact that such transactions may affect the company's activities, its financial results, as well as the assessment of the company's activities by users of the financial reporting). In 1988, IAS 26 "Accounting and Reporting on Pension Plans" came into force, taking into account the changes of 1998. and reflecting how to evaluate and disclose information about pension plans in the financial statements. In 1990, (IAS) 28 "Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures" began to operate, which describes the accounting procedure for such investments; and (IAS) 29 "Financial Reporting in a Hyperinflationary Economy", which establishes that financial statements at the time of the reporting date should be provided in current currency units (i.e. the currency of the country with hyperinflationary economy is the functional currency of the enterprise). In 1993 and 1994 (IAS) 2 "Inventories" were published, respectively, which was to enter into force on January 1, 2005 and which established the rules for accounting for inventories; and (IAS) 7 "Cash Flow Statement", which entered into force immediately from 1994, describing the change in the company's cash for the period and dividing cash flows into financial, operational and investment activities. In 1995, IAS 32 "Financial Instruments: Presentation of Information" was issued, an improved version of which re-entered into force in 2005. This standard contains requirements for the presentation of information on financial instruments that are financial liabilities or capital instruments, as well as requirements for offsetting financial instruments. (IAS) 33 "Earnings per Share" was published in 1997 and was supposed to come into force in 1999. This standard defines how to calculate basic and diluted earnings per share. In 1998, IAS 39 "Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement" was issued, the amendments of which entered into force in 2005.

(this standard is limited to 2018, it will be subsequently replaced by IFRS 9) and which sets out the rules for the measurement, recognition and derecognition of financial assets and liabilities. And finally, a number of standards were issued in 1999: (IAS) 34 "Interim Financial Statements", which establishes minimum requirements for the content, rules for accounting recognition and valuation; (IAS) 36 "Impairment of assets", which consists in establishing the procedure that the company applies in order to account for its assets at the amount not exceeding their recoverable value; The standard also determines when an entity should recover (reverse) an impairment loss on an asset and prescribes certain disclosure requirements; (IAS) 37 "Reserves, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent assets" and (IAS) 38 "Intangible assets", which reflects the accounting treatment of such assets. Thus, we see that during the period from 1973 to 2000, the Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards did extensive work on the development of key standards. However, the main step towards the dissemination and implementation of the developed principles in the USA was the Norwalk Agreement, signed in 2002 by the IASB and FASB, which outlined the first aspirations for convergence of the two standards. The development of convergence of IFRS and US GAAP during the George W. Bush administration (2002 - January 2009), George W. Bush assumed the presidency of the United States on January 20, 2001, and with his arrival is associated with the beginning of the development of close relations between the IASB and FASB [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014, p. Later, in 2005, Donald Nicolason, the SEC's chief accountant, first mentioned the so-called roadmap the relationship between IASB and FASB (Convergence Development Plan) in his article "A Securities Regulator Looks at Convergence" [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014]. This plan included the conditions, prerequisites and a key requirement for achieving the adoption of SEC IFRS (it was the need for the same

quality of financial statements prepared, on the one hand, in accordance with US GAAP, and, on the other hand, in accordance with IFRS). In addition, the plan mentioned for the first time the possibility of European companies not providing a document of approval with US GAAP.

В 2002–2009 гг. ранее начатые отношения между IASB и FASB развивались очень стремительно, однако случившееся в 2009 г. торможение отношений переросло к 2012 г. в застой.

Conclusion

1. In this paper, an attempt was made to analyze the development of the convergence of US GAAP and IFRS in stages, the results of which can answer the following questions: Are IFRS as perfect as it may seem at first glance?

2. Do American and international accounting standards have the same quality?

3. Is the world in general and the USA in particular ready for high rates of integration and unification of accounting standards? As it was shown in the work, in the period from 2002 to 2009 The USA was ready for the rapid convergence of the two accounting systems, as evidenced by the close relationship between the two main boards - IASB and FASB, which resulted in the resolution of many plans, goals, the cancellation of the document of approval with US GAAP and the general recognition of IFRS as the only possible standards representing the high quality of the work of IASB, which, combining standards from different countries, developing new and improving the final standards, seeks to obtain high-quality and reliable standards, thereby creating a unified world of accounting. However, criticism of the convergence gaining momentum was also expressed during the George W. Bush administration. In particular, in 2007, former SEC chief accountant Lin Turner stated that convergence success could be achieved only if the two accounting systems were truly comparable, but there are too many "holes" in the accounting guidelines in

different industries [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014, p. 16]. Also, SEC Chairman Mary Shapiro, appointed by Barack Obama, in early 2009. expressed concern about the cost of switching to a different accounting regime that companies will have to pay (according to SEC estimates, such costs may reach \$32 million for some enterprises) [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014, p. 16] and about the independence of the IASB (i.e. independent development and adoption of standards, as well as their convergence with the US GAAP was questioned due to the structure of the IASC, which was described above, as well as due to the possibility of independent financing of the committee). In addition, concerns were expressed about the unsustainable nature of IFRS, which were based solely on principles. The period from 2009 to the end of 2012 differs, on the contrary, by the unwillingness of the United States to such rates of convergence. The result of such unwillingness was the suspension of the convergence of the two standards (formally, the SEC developed a plan for the transition to new standards, but the exact date of this transition was not announced). According to the SEC, an additional analysis of IFRS, their impact on the US securities market and investors after the final adoption of IFRS, as well as the difference between US GAAP and IFRS, was required. As for questions about the quality of international and American accounting standards, in order to determine the applicability of IFRS in the world, the SEC analyzed the financial statements of 183 companies located in 22 countries (the companies were selected from the Fortune Global 500 list in 2009; 80% of these companies were located in the EU, and companies from Australia, Brazil and China were also represented), which prepared financial statements in accordance with IFRS [Erchinger, 2012, p. 254]. However, the SEC's analysis was limited to the information disclosed in the financial statements; in particular, in many cases, SEC management simply could not determine how some transactions were reflected in the statements and whether the

company's accounting policy complies with IFRS. As a result of this analysis, management concluded that, in general, the financial statements comply with the requirements of IFRS, but the clarity and transparency of transactions of some companies and disclosure of information about the accounting policies applied can be improved (i.e., some companies did not provide information about accounting policies in certain areas of activity, and clarifying accounting policy details were not provided, which could would help investors and other users to fully and clearly understand the financial statements. In addition, terminology other than the established terminology of IFRS was used). The SEC also concluded that the diverse application of IFRS creates difficulties in comparability and comparison of financial statements of different industries and different countries. Moreover, as already noted above, the very basis of IFRS - principles - may be the reason for the creation of standards of not as high quality as required by the United States, i.e. While US GAAP is based on rules, providing accurate guidance on most operations to companies from completely different industries, IFRS offers meager, inaccurate and non-extensive guidance especially for some industries (for example, insurance) [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014, p. 17-19]. As stated by Zidman, the US financial system requires more accuracy than IFRS can offer [McEnroe and Sullivan, 2014, p. 19]. Summing up, it should be said that, firstly, as the SEC study showed, IFRS are not high-quality standards, since many provisions can be improved; secondly, in some cases, US GAAP are of higher quality than IFRS (the reason may be rooted in the different basis of IFRS and US GAAP, as well as in the US financial culture, which for many years was based solely on rules, but did not act based on principles); and, thirdly, that in different periods the US was differently configured to integrate accounting systems. Some authors see the reason for the change in the direction of the attitude of the SEC and the United States as a whole towards convergence in the

global financial crisis that began in 2008 and as a result of which completely different priority goals appeared. However, both periods were necessary in order to identify the weaknesses of IFRS and the bodies that develop and adopt them, because economic globalization is only gaining momentum, which means that very soon there may be an urgent need for unified high-quality accounting standards, although this need already exists. The attempt to converge two qualitative accounting standards has led to the fact that IFRS will be further improved to become the basis for a unified accounting world.

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